

Supplementary Figure 4

Supplementary Fig. 4. Quantitative analysis of miR-155 in situ hybridization in the dentate gyrus (DG, **A**) or CA1 area (**B**) of resected brain tissue of patients with TLE-HS showed a trend towards upregulation in the DG. Mann-Whitney U test, error bars depict the standard error of the mean.